

Cyclic voltammetric study of the oxidation of quinizarin in the presence of cyanide ion

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Abstract : Electrochemical oxidation of 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone has been studied in the presence of cyanide ion as nucleophile in water/acetonitrile (50 : 50) solution, by means of cyclic voltammetry as a diagnostic technique. The results indicate participation of the produced anthraquinone in the Michael reaction with cyanide ion and via an EC mechanism removes the cyanide ion in the media. This reaction is useful for removing the harmful effect of cyanide ion. To estimate the homogeneous rate constant of the Michael reaction, electrochemical oxidation of 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone in the presence of cyanide ion was tested by digital simulation. Based on an EC mechanism, the homogeneous rate constant was estimated by comparing the experimental cyclic voltammetric responses with the digital simulated results.

Keywords : 1,4-Dihydroxyanthraquinone, cyclic voltammetry, digital simulation, cyanide ion.

Introduction

The cyanide ion is an extremely hazardous material that damages by absorption through the lungs, gastrointestinal track, and skin and can kill mammals upon binding to a heme unit¹. It strongly binds to cytochrome-c and disrupts the mitochondrial electron-transport chain, leading to decreased oxidative metabolism and oxygen utilization^{2,3}. The cyanide ion also adversely affects vascular, visual, central nervous, cardiac, endocrine and metabolic functions⁴⁻⁶. Humans may be exposed to cyanides from dietary, industrial, environmental and other sources. Consequently, there is a growing interest in sensing the presence of the toxic cyanide anion by coordination or covalent bonds. On the other hand, hydroxyanthraquinones are of general interest as dyes and pigments⁷ and as model chromophores for biologically active compounds, such as the anthracycline antitumor drugs. It is the main part in the chemical structure of daunorubicin, doxorubicin and mitoxantrone. These drugs exhibit biological activity by intercalation of the anthracycline aromatic moiety between the DNA base pairs, resulting in the inhibition of transcription by blockage of RNA polymerase⁸⁻¹⁰. The results of this paper show that electrogenerated anthraquinone

participate in a reaction with cyanide ion, so this reaction is useful for removing the harmful effect of cyanide ion. The purpose of this work is the kinetic and mechanistic study of the electrochemical oxidation of 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone in the presence of cyanide ion and the estimation of the observed homogeneous rate constants (k_{obs}) of reaction of electrochemically generated *anthraquinone* with this nucleophile by digital simulation of cyclic voltammograms.

Experimental

Reagents and material :

All chemicals (potassium cyanide and 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone) were reagent-grade materials from commercial sources and acetate salts and other inorganic salts were of pro-analysis grade from E. Merck. These chemicals were used without further purification.

Instrumentation :

Cyclic voltammetry was performed using an Autolab model PGSTAT 20 potentiostat/golvanostat. The working electrode used in the voltammetry experiments was a glassy carbon disc (1.8 mm diameter) and platinum wire was used as the counter electrode. The working electrode

potentials were measured versus SCE (from AZAR electrode). The homogeneous rate constants were estimated by analyzing the cyclic voltammetric responses using the simulation DIGIELCH software¹¹.

Results and discussion

Electrochemical study :

Fig. 1 (curve a), shows cyclic voltammogram recorded for 0.5 mM 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (**1**) in water/ acetonitrile (50/50) solution containing 0.2 M acetate buffer solution (pH 5.0). The voltammogram shows an anodic peak (A_1) in the positive-going scan and a cathodic counterpart peak (C_1) in the negative-going scan which corresponds to the transformation of 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (**1**) to anthraquinone (**1a**) and vice-versa within a quasi-reversible two-electron process (Scheme 1, eq. 1). In this condition, peak current ratio (I_{pC_1}/I_{pA_1}) is less than unity and decreases with decreasing the potential sweep rate indicating that **1a** is not stable in the time scale of our experiments. This instability is related to the presence of two fused quinonic rings in the structure of **1a**. We have shown previously that, the presence of the electron-withdrawing group on the quinone rings enhanced the following chemical reactions such as oxidative ring cleavage¹²⁻¹⁵. The presence of two fused quinonic rings enhances the rate of ring cleavage, so that the effect of

this reaction is observed in the time scale of our cyclic voltammetry.

The oxidation of 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (**1**) in the presence of cyanide ion as a nucleophile was studied in some details. Fig. 1 (curve b) shows the cyclic voltammogram obtained for a 0.5 mM solution of **1** in the presence of 10 mM cyanide ion. In these conditions, the cathodic counterpart of the anodic peak A_1 decreases dramatically. Furthermore, it is seen that proportional to the augmentation of potential sweep rate, the height of C_1 peak of **1** increase (Fig. 2, curves a-d). A plot of the peak current ratio (I_{pC}/I_{pA}) versus ν for a mixture of 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (**1**) and cyanide ion confirms the reactivity of **1** towards cyanide ion appearing as a decrease in peak current ratio (I_{pC}/I_{pA}) at higher scan rates (Fig. 2, inset). In the cyclic voltammetric method, the potential scan rate is an effective experimental parameter which can be used to control τ , a measure of the period during which a stable electroactive species can communicate with the electrode. By increasing the scan rate this characteristic time is limited compared to t , which t is the characteristic lifetime of a coupled chemical reaction.

Fig. 3 shows cyclic voltammograms of **1** in the presence of various amounts of cyanide ion. As shown, the

Fig. 1. (a) Cyclic voltammogram of 0.5 mM 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (**1**) in the absence and (b) in the presence of 10 mM cyanide ion (**2**) at a glassy carbon electrode in water/ acetonitrile (50 : 50) solution containing acetate buffer ($c = 0.2 M$, pH 5), scan rate : 100 mV/s, $t = 25 \pm 1$ °C.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of 0.5 mM 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (**1**) in the presence of 10 mM cyanide ion (**2**) in various scan rates at a glassy carbon electrode, in water/ acetonitrile (50/50) solution containing acetate buffer ($c = 0.2 M$, pH = 5). Scan rates from (a) to (d) are : 10, 25, 50 and 75 mV/s. Inset : variation of peak current ratio (I_{pC}/I_{pA}) versus scan rate, $t = 25 \pm 1$ °C.

height of cathodic peak (C_1) decreases by increasing cyanide concentration.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (1) in different concentrations of cyanide ion, in water/acetonitrile (50/50) solution containing acetate buffer ($c = 0.2 M$, $pH = 5$). Concentrations from (a) to (b) are : 5, 10, 20 and 30 mM. Scan rate : 100 mV/s. Inset, variation of peak current ratio (I_{pc}/I_{pa}) versus cyanide ion concentration, $t = 25 \pm 1 ^\circ C$.

Our results indicate the reaction of cyanide ion with 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone, and the previous published paper¹⁶ allow us to suggest the mechanism presented in Scheme 1. It seems that *electrogenerated* anthraquinone participate in a reaction with cyanide ion via 1,4-Michael addition.

Scheme 1

Kinetic study :

Electrochemical oxidation of 1 in the presence of cyanide ion was tested by digital simulation. The simulation was carried out assuming semiinfinite one-dimensional diffusion and planar electrode geometry. The experimental parameters entered for digital simulation consisted of the following : E_{start} , E_{switch} , E_{end} , $t = 25 ^\circ C$ and analytical concentration of 1. The transfer coefficient (α) was assumed to be about 0.5 and the formal potentials were obtained experimentally as the midpoint potential between the anodic and cathodic peaks (E_{mid}). All these parameters were kept constant throughout the fitting of the digitally simulated voltammogram to the experimental data. The parameter k_{obs} was allowed to change through the fitting processes. The simulation was performed base on an EC electrochemical mechanism under pseudo-first order conditions (Fig. 4, curves a and b).

Fig. 4 (curve c), shows that the pseudo-first order rate constants increase linearly with the increasing of concentration of cyanide ion. The second order rate constants ($k_{obs}/M^{-1} s^{-1}$) were determined from the slope of the best fit line on this curve¹⁷⁻²⁰. The calculated value of second order rate constants for reaction of 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (1) with cyanide ion is $5.7 M^{-1} s^{-1}$.

Conclusion

The results of this work show that 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (1) is oxidized in water/acetonitrile (50/50) solution to their respective *anthraquinone*. The anthraquinone are then attacked by the cyanide ion. The kinetics of the reactions of electrochemically generated *anthraquinone*, with cyanide ion is studied by the cyclic voltammetric technique and the simulation of obtained voltammograms performed under EC mechanism. There is a good agreement between the simulated voltammograms with those obtained experimentally. Also, the observed homogeneous rate constant (k_{obs}) of reaction of electrochemically generated anthraquinone with cyanide ion was estimated by digital simulation of cyclic voltammograms.

Fig. 4. Experimental and simulated cyclic voltammograms of 0.5 mM 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (1) in the presence of (a) 20 mM cyanide ion and scan rate 50 mV/s. (b) 5 mM cyanide ion and scan rate = 10 mV/s. Curve c : linear relation between k_{obs} and concentration of cyanide ion.

References

1. K. S. Lee, H. J. Kim, G. H. Kim, I. Shin and J. I. Hong, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 49.
2. Y. Shiraishi, K. Adachi, M. Itoh and T. Hirai, *Org. Lett.*, 2009, **11**, 3482.
3. R. Koenig, *Science*, 2000, **287**, 1737.
4. S. Saha, A. Ghosh, P. Mahato, S. Mishra, S. K. Mishra, E. Suresh, S. Das and A. Das, *Org. Lett.*, 2010, **12**, 3406.
5. D. G. Cho, J. H. Kim and J. L. Sessler, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **130**, 12163.
6. M. R. Ajayakumar and P. Mokhopadhyay, *Org. Lett.*, 2010, **12**, 2646.
7. D. D. Nguyen, N. C. Jones, S. V. Hoffman and J. S. Larsen, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2010, **77**, 279.
8. G. Fabriciova, J. V. G. Ramos, P. Miskovsky and S. S. Cortes, *Vibrational Spectroscopy*, 2004, **34**, 273.
9. B. J. Stefafiska, M. J. Dzieduszycka, S. Martelli, I. Antonini and E. Borowski, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 1568.
10. S. S. Massoud and R. B. Jordan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 4851.
11. M. Rudolph, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2002, **97**, 529 (also see www.digielch.de).
12. F. Varmaghani and D. Nematollahi, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2011, **56**, 6089.
13. D. Nematollahi and F. Varmaghani, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2008, **53**, 3350.
14. D. Nematollahi and F. Varmaghani, *J. Iran. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **8**, 803.
15. D. Nematollahi, A. Sayadi and F. Varmaghani, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2012, **671**, 44.

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16. D. Nematollahi, M. Alimoradi and S. Waqif Husain, 2004, **16**, 1359.
17. E. S. Gawalt and M. Mrksich, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 15613.
18. Y. Kwon and M. Mrksich, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 806.
19. M. N. Yousaf, E. W. L. Chan and M. Mrksich, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2000, **39**, 1943.
20. M. N. Yousaf and M. Mrksich, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **121**, 4286.
21. D. Nematollahi, M. S. Workentin and E. Tammari, *Chem. Commun.*, 2006, 1631.

